

Synthesis, spectral, thermal and antimicrobial studies of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes with 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxy-4-methylphenylazo)-5-pyrazolone

M. L. Hari Kumaran Nair* and V. L. Siji

Department of Chemistry, University College, Thiruvananthapuram-695 034, Kerala, India

E-mail : drmlhnair@gmail.com

Manuscript received 17 December 2007, revised 9 April 2008, accepted 15 April 2008

Abstract : Some novel oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of the formulae $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{ClO}_4)\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{CMCAAP})\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NCS})]$, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NO}_3)]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (where CMCAAP = para-chlorometacresolazoantipyrine) have been synthesised and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility data, IR, UV-visible, ESR and ^1H NMR spectral studies. The thermal properties of the complex was investigated by thermogravimetric technique. The ligand and the complexes were screened for their possible antibacterial and antifungal activities. The complexes are found to be monomeric with distorted octahedral geometry.

Keywords : Oxomolybdenum(V), dioxomolybdenum(VI), thermal studies.

Introduction

Molybdenum is a versatile transition element because it possesses a large number of stable and accessible oxidation states¹. The Mo sites are supposed to be active centers for the catalytic activity of the enzymes². The higher oxidation states of Mo are dominated by complexes that contain the molybdenum oxo groups, monooxo (MoO^{3+}) and *cis*-dioxo (MoO_2^{2+}) species.

Owing to the importance of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, we have isolated and characterized a few new complexes of a potential multidentate ligand, 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxy-4-methylphenylazo)-5-pyrazolone CMCAAP (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

All the complexes are deeply coloured, non-hygroscopic solids. They are soluble in nitrobenzene and acetonitrile, sparingly soluble in other common organic solvents and insoluble in ether. The analytical data are in agreement with the compositions proposed for the complexes in Table 1. The molar conductance data (Table 1) show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes. The magnetic moments (Table 1) of Mo^{V} complexes are in the range of 1.70–1.78 B.M. which correspond to the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) and indicated the absence of any Mo–Mo interaction³. All the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes are diamagnetic as expected.

Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignments of ligand and their metal complexes. The infrared spectrum of the free ligand exhibited a broad medium intensity band $\sim 3182\text{ cm}^{-1}$, assignable to hydrogen bonded -OH group⁴. This band is absent in the spectra of all the complexes. This may be due to the participation of -OH group in coordination via deprotonation with the metal.

The IR spectra of the complexes showed no absorption in the region $3500\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the involvement of the phenolic group in coordination with the metal⁵. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ phenolic modes of the ligand appearing in the region $\sim 1274\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are shifted to higher frequency

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the molybdenum complexes

Complex (Colour)	Analytical data (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Mo	Cl	C	H	N	S	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$	CH_3CN	CH_3OH	
[MoO(CMCAAP)Cl ₂] (Brown)	17.76 (17.82)	13.11 (13.17)	40.10 (40.16)	2.81 (3.18)	10.98 (10.40)		9.2	10.1	5.8	1.78
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NCS)Cl] (Reddish brown)	17.02 (17.10)	6.14 (6.32)	40.13 (40.68)	2.11 (2.88)	12.23 (12.49)	5.06 (5.72)	10.4	12.4	6.2	1.72
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NO ₃)Cl] (Brown)	16.83 (16.98)	6.04 (6.28)	38.23 (38.28)	2.81 (2.85)	9.21 (9.91)		11.1	10.9	7.9	1.76
[MoO(CMCAAP)(ClO ₄)Cl] (Brownish red)	15.16 (15.93)	5.75 (5.89)	35.81 (35.89)	2.62 (2.67)	9.29 (9.30)		10.3	14.2	4.1	1.71
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)Cl] (Brown)	18.31 (18.49)	6.73 (6.83)	41.67 (41.66)	3.02 (3.10)	10.68 (10.79)		3.6	9.2	12.8	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NCS)] (Reddish brown)	17.09 (17.72)		42.03 (42.15)	2.69 (2.98)	12.87 (12.93)	5.61 (5.92)	3.8	7.8	11.6	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NO ₃)] (Brown)	17.48 (17.59)						2.8	2.8	9.8	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(ClO ₄)] (Brownish red)	15.96 (16.46)						4.5	6.5	6.9	Diamagnetic

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligand CMCAAP and oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes

Ligand/Complexes	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})							
	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{sym(O=Mo=O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{asym(O=Mo=O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$
CMCAAP	3182	1645	1490	-	-	-	-	-
[MoO(CMCAAP)Cl ₂]	-	1591	1454	960	-	-	501	440
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NCS)Cl]	-	1581	1460	962	-	-	501	440
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NO ₃)Cl]	-	1585	1454	958	-	-	501	440
[MoO(CMCAAP)(ClO ₄)Cl]	-	1591	1454	960	-	-	501	445
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)Cl]	-	1570	1454	-	948	910	501	416
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NCS)]	-	1591	1454	-	950	900	501	415
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NO ₃)]	-	1580	1455	-	941	910	501	410
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(ClO ₄)]	-	1579	1453	-	942	906	500	400

in the complexes indicating complex formation via deprotonation⁶ of phenolic -OH. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ observed at 1645 cm^{-1} and 1490 cm^{-1} respectively in the ligand spectrum are shifted to $\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1455 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes, suggesting the participation of these groups in coordination. Thus the ligand CMCAAP acts as an anionic tridentate chelating agent in all the complexes.

A very strong band observed at 960 cm^{-1} in the spectra of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes corresponds to Mo=O stretching frequency⁵. The strong bands exhibited by dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes in the region $940\text{--}950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $900\text{--}910 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to the ν_{sym}

(O=Mo=O) and ν_{asym} (O=Mo=O). The IR spectra indicate the presence of a *cis*-MoO₂ structure⁷. The Mo-N stretching frequency lies at 500 cm^{-1} in the complexes. Medium to weak intensity bands $\sim 440\text{--}450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 430\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$ in oxomolybdenum(V) complexes and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes respectively⁸.

The IR spectra of the nitrate complexes are suggestive of mono-coordinated nitrate group⁹ ($\nu_4 \sim 1532$, $\nu_1 \sim 1394$ and $\nu_2 \sim 1034 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In the spectra of the thiocyanate complexes, the bands at 2060 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, 765 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and 468 cm^{-1} δ_{NCS} indicate the N-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group¹⁰. The bands at 1150 (ν_4), 1050

(ν_1), 698 (ν_3) and 624 (ν_5) in spectra of the perchlorate complexes are suggestive of monodentate coordination¹¹.

The electronic spectral bands of oxomolybdenum(v) complexes in solution together with the tentative assignments are discussed¹². The Mo^V complexes usually exhibit three distinct absorption bands in the region 13500–14500, 19000–22000 and 22500–26000 cm^{-1} , assignable to the transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$). Usually the third band is obscured by the more intense charge transfer transition $O(\pi) \rightarrow d(\text{Mo})$ involving the excitation of an electron from the highest filled π -bonding M.O (associated mainly with oxygen) to the d orbitals of Mo. All the present Mo^V complexes show bands in the region 15384–15924, 20366–21141 and 25316–26041 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectra thus indicate octahedral environment for all the complexes and are in conformity with the Ballhausen-Gray scheme for an octahedral geometry. No bands are observed below 10000 cm^{-1} and hence the possibility of a tetrahedral structure can be ruled out. The complexes can be best considered as octahedral with strong tetragonal distortion (C_{4v} symmetry), resulting from the Mo=O multiple bond.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand displays two sharp signals which correspond to the methyl protons. $>\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ group of pyrazolone ring appears as a sharp singlet in the region δ (2.20–2.41). Another sharp singlet in the region δ (3.11–3.31) corresponds to the proton of $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ group. The aromatic rings give a group of multi signals at δ (6.8–7.6). The ligand shows a peak at δ (9.71), characteristic of intramolecular hydrogen bonded -OH

proton. The analysis of the spectrum of the complex reveals that there is no signal in the region δ (9.71). Thus it can be concluded that the -OH group coordinates to the metal via deprotonation¹³. The IR spectral data are also in conformity with these observations.

The ESR spectrum of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$ which was recorded in polycrystalline form at room temperature, exhibited a single line only. The ESR parameters were found to be $g_{\parallel} = 1.998$, $g_{\perp} = 1.912$ and $g_{av} = 1.940$. The g_{av} value indicates that the pentavalent Mo in the complex is monomeric¹⁴.

Thermal behaviour of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}]$ was studied by TGA in air at a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in conjunction with DTG (Fig. 2).

The complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}]$ undergoes a two stage decomposition as indicated by the DTG peaks at 296.92 $^{\circ}$ and 434.91 $^{\circ}$. The first stage of decomposition is from 230 $^{\circ}$ to 340 $^{\circ}$ in the TG curve which corresponds to the elimination of coordinated species CMCAAP and coordinated Cl^- ion and in the second stage (380–460 $^{\circ}$) the complete decomposition of the complex to MoO_3 takes place. The final mass loss observed agrees with the values calculated for the conversion of the complex to its oxide (MoO_3). The order parameters for the first and second stages of decomposition are two. The energy of activation for the first stage of decomposition is 106.6 kJ mol^{-1} and that of second stage of decomposition is 277.7 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. The ΔS values for the two stages of decomposition are 907.2 and 696.2 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively¹⁵. The computational details and the kinetic parameters of the two stages of thermal decomposition of

Fig. 2. TG (—) and DTG (---) curves of $[\text{MoO}(\text{CMCAAP})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}]$.

Table 3. Kinetic parameters for two stages of thermal decomposition of [MoO(CMCAAP)(NO₃)Cl]

Stages	Peak temp. (K)	Activation energy, <i>E</i> (kJ/mol)	Pre-exponential factor, <i>A</i> (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation, Δ <i>S</i> (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
1	569.92	106.605	4.85 × 10 ⁷	-907.227
2	707.91	277.777	6.32 × 10 ¹⁸	-696.249

the complex are given in Table 3.

The ligand CMCAAP and the complexes [MoO(CMCAAP)(NCS)Cl], [MoO(CMCAAP)(NO₃)Cl], [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NCS)] and [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NO₃)] have been screened for their possible antibacterial activities by Disc Diffusion Method¹⁶ (Kirby Bauer Method) against *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 12666, *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *Salmonella typhi* ATCC 35987, *Pseudomonas fluorescence* ATCC 10796, *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 51912 and *Serratia marcescens* ATCC 12294 at 10 μg per disc using pencillin as positive control and chloroform as negative control. The test results (Table 4) show that the ligand CMCAAP did not exhibit any antibacterial activities and the complexes exhibit antibacterial activities.

The antifungal activities of the ligand CMCAAP and the complexes [MoO(CMCAAP)(NO₃)Cl] and [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NCS)] were tested against *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 1027 and *Penicillium sp.* ATCC 10115 by Disc Diffusion method at a concentration of 10 μg per disc using gresiofulvin as positive control and chloroform as negative control. The test results (Table 5) show the ligand CMCAAP and the complex [MoO(CMCAAP)(NO₃)Cl] did not exhibit any antifungal activities. But the complex [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NCS)] showed antifungal activity against *Penicillium sp.* only at a concentration of 10 μg per disc giving a zone of inhibition of 18 mm.

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, a distorted octahedral geometry is suggested for these complexes.

Table 4. Test results of antibacterial activities of the ligand CMCAAP and the complexes [MoO(CMCAAP)(NCS)Cl], [MoO(CMCAAP)(NO₃)Cl], [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NCS)] and [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NO₃)]

Test sample		Zone of inhibition					
		<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> ATCC 12666	<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	<i>Salmonella typhi</i> ATCC 35987	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescence</i> ATCC 10796	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> ATCC 51912	<i>Serratia marcescens</i> ATCC 12294
CMCAAP	10 μg	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NCS)Cl]	10 μg	10 mm	Nil	10 mm	10 mm	9 mm	9 mm
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NO ₃)Cl]	10 μg	19 mm	Nil	17 mm	16 mm	19 mm	15 mm
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NCS)]	10 μg	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	10 mm
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NO ₃)]	10 μg	9 mm	21 mm	15 mm	17 mm	21 mm	25 mm
Negative control (chloroform)		Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Pencillin 10 mcg		12 mm	14 mm	10 mm	19 mm	30 mm	20 mm

Table 5. Test results of antifungal activities of the ligand CMCAAP and the complexes [MoO(CMCAAP)(NO₃)Cl] and [MoO₂(CMCAAP)(NCS)]

Test sample		Zone of inhibition	
		<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> ATCC 1027	<i>Penicillium sp.</i> ATCC 10115
CMCAAP	10 μg	Nil	Nil
[MoO(CMCAAP)(NO ₃)Cl]	10 μg	Nil	Nil
[MoO ₂ (CMCAAP)(NCS)]	10 μg	Nil	18 mm
Negative control (chloroform)		Nil	Nil
Gresiofulvin 10 mcg		23 mm	20 mm

Fig. 3. Suggested structures for oxomolybdenum(v) and dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes of CMCAAP.

Experimental

MoCl₅ (Aldrich Chemicals, USA), MoO₃ (Lobo Chemie, Mumbai), 4-aminoantipyrene (E. Merck, Germany), *p*-chloro-*m*-cresol (Sisco Research Laboratory, Mumbai) were used as such. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligand CMCAAP was synthesized from 4-aminoantipyrene and *p*-chloro-*m*-cresol by diazotisation and coupling as described in the literature¹⁷.

Oxomolybdenum(v) complexes : A methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (2 mmol) was mixed with the ligand (2 mmol) in hot methanol and refluxed for ~2 h. The solid which separated on concentrating the solution, was suction filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of the thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate

complexes. By adding a methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (2 mmol) containing ~0.5 g of NH₄CNS/~0.5 g of LiNO₃/3-4 drops of perchloric acid as the case may be, to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring. The resulted solution was heated over water bath for ~1 h. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed several times with aqueous methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

Dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes : These complexes were prepared in the same manner as the oxomolybdenum(v) complexes. The general method adopted for the preparation of the thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate complexes was also the same.

Metal, chloride, perchlorate and sulphur contents in the complexes were estimated by standard methods¹⁸. Elemental analyses were carried out at Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Centre, Kochi. The IR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in the region 4000–400 cm⁻¹ on a Shimadzu IR Prestige-21 spectrometer. The electronic spectra of the complexes in methanol were recorded on JASCO V-550 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Japan) in the range 900–200 nm. The conductance value of the complexes in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (*ca.* 10⁻³ M) were measured using digital control dynamics conductivity meter. ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded in CDCl₃ on a 300 MHz Bruker Avance-300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference material. ESR spectrum of the complex was run on a Varian E-112X - Q band spectrometer with DPPH as a reference material. The magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature were measured on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections for various atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal's constants. The thermal decomposition study was made using a Mettler TG-50 thermobalance in air at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the ligand and the complexes were tested by disc diffusion method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to RRL, Thiruvananthapuram; STIC, Kochi; IIT, Chennai; Department of Chemistry, University of Kerala, Kariavattom; Government Drug Testing Laboratory, Thiruvananthapuram; MCC, Mariagiri, Kanyakumari, T.N. and VSSC, Thiruvananthapuram for the facilities.

References

1. E. I. Steifel, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 22, 1; M. L. Harikumar Nair and C. P. Prabhakaran, *J. Teach. Res.*

- Chem.*, 1996, **3**, 25; M. R. Maurya and C. Gopinathan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 701.
2. D. J. A. Raj, K. S. Nagaraja and M. R. Udupa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 869.
 3. M. L. Harikumar Nair and K. R. Kumari Nisha, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2007, **19**, 4689; A. Sheela, M. S. Pramila Gladis and M. L. Harikumar Nair, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 329; A. Syamal and S. Ahmed, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 460; B. N. Figgis and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4190.
 4. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 1978.
 5. M. L. Harikumar Nair and C. P. Prabhakaran, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 452; D. D. Agarwal, Rachana Rastogi, V. K. Gupta and S. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 369.
 6. V. M. Naik and N. B. Mallur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 780.
 7. F. A. Cotton and R. M. Wing, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 867; M. L. Harikumar Nair, PhD Thesis, University of Kerala, 1993.
 8. C. P. Prabhakaran and B. G. Nair, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1983, **8**, 368; K. C. Satpathi, R. Mishra and B. B. Jal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 697.
 9. Sali Thomas and M. L. Harikumar Nair, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2005, **17**, 2657; C. C. Addison, R. Davis and N. Logan, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 3333; N. F. Curtius and Y. M. Curtius, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 804.
 10. A. Sabatini and I. Bertini, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1960, **5**, 204.
 11. D. K. Koppikar, P. V. Sivapulliaiah, L. Ramakrishnan and S. Soundararajan, *Struct. Bonding*, 1978, **34**, 135.
 12. C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111; C. R. Hare, I. Bernal and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 568.
 13. William Kemp, "NMR in Chemistry, A Multinuclear Introduction", MC. Millan Publishing Company, 1986; D. H. Williams and I. Fleming, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi, 1988.
 14. W. Gordge, "Theory and Applications of Electron Spin Resonance", John Wiley, New York, 1980; P. Verma, K. K. Arya and S. Ahmad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 327.
 15. C. P. Prabhakaran and M. L. Harikumar Nair, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 7; A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.
 16. R. Ananthanarayan and J. C. Panikar, "Text Book of Microbiology", Orient Longman, 1999, 578.
 17. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., ELBS, 1994, p. 946.
 18. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., ELBS with Longman, 1996, p. 461.